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**FROM ONE UNION TO ANOTHER –
POSTCOLONIAL LEGACIES AND
ESTONIAN EU MEMBERSHIP**

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What has caused these understandings of Estonia in the EU and the EU in Estonia is the main question of this paper. It tries to unpack the precarious relationship between sovereignty, security and EU law primacy claims as the main constitutional conundrums of the Estonian EU membership and European constitutional imaginaries. What feeds into some ontological insecurities and idiosyncratic understandings of sovereignty in the country? It proposes that the country's postcolonial predicament might be a way to explain these puzzles.

KEYWORDS: Estonia, constitutional imaginary of Europe, legacy of empire, Homo Sovieticus

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From one Union to another – postcolonial legacies and Estonian EU membership

Birgit Aasa¹

Introduction

The European Union (EU) is imbued by the legacy of the empire. Practically all of its Member States have been either former colonial powers or former colonial subjects. The eastern part of the EU has a specific baggage and legacy that it brings to the EU. After 1989 the smaller and bigger countries of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) have undergone major transformations from being *homo Sovieticus* to becoming a fully-fledged member of the European family and ‘the West’. All countries have chosen their own specific paths in this journey, some recently more problematic than others. Estonia is an example of arguably one of the most Europhile paths of them all. This because of a need and want to be a ‘good European’ and it can be traced in both national grand narratives and more practical court practice.

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Constitutional imaginaries in the context of this study can be defined as the manner in which constitutions can harness the power of narrative, symbol, ritual and myth to project an account of political existence in ways that shape – and re-shape – political reality.² They are preceded by wider notions of social and cultural imaginaries, the first of which according to Charles Taylor refer to ‘the ways people imagine their social existence, how they fit together, how things go on between them and their fellows, the expectations that are normally met, and the deeper normative notions and images that underlie these expectations.’³ Cultural imaginaries have been conceptualised as consisting of the shared images and narratives of the past, patterns of behaviour for the present, and visions for the national future that together shape the self-conception of the community.⁴ Estonian European constitutional imaginaries are therefore a set of deeply held beliefs, drawn narratives and discourses that justify, explain and condition Estonian EU membership and the obligations deriving therefrom. These imaginaries are narrated, reproduced and replicated at the level of the nation’s social and cultural imaginaries.

What is the main socially and politically narrated reality in Estonia regarding its EU membership? What are the dynamics at play when salient decisions about either EU law or national constitutional primacy are held? Several circumstantial aspects could be listed in this regard, but I consider three to be the most relevant: security, sovereignty and postcoloniality. These predicaments condition Estonian EU membership and understanding of Europe and its place in it. This paper argues that the main underlying condition for Estonia’s unconventional European constitutional imaginary has been the securitization of sovereignty due to its postcolonial history. This background has to be taken into account also by the EU in its approach to the post-Soviet sphere as it causes ontological anxieties and different understandings of nationalism, security and sovereignty that may differ from the same understandings of the EU’s center.

¹ This paper is written as a part of the European Research Council (ERC) funded project IMAGINE (European Constitutional Imaginaries: Utopias, Ideologies and the Other), grant agreement no 803163. All errors and omissions are mine alone.

² Martin Loughlin, ‘The Constitutional Imagination’ (2015) 78 *The Modern Law Review* 1, 3.

³ Charles Taylor, *Modern Social Imaginaries* (Duke University Press 2004) 23.

⁴ Epp Annus “Estonians’ European imaginaries: the Soviet legacy” in edited volume, forthcoming.

Being a formerly colonized periphery brings along idiosyncratic legacies and experiences that might also bear significance to a country's membership in the EU and for the EU itself as the EU is a sum of its parts – all parts, however tiny or seemingly unsubstantial.

The paper proceeds in five parts. First, the status of being a 'good European' is unpacked and explained. Second, the relationship between sovereignty and security is exemplified as a source of ontological insecurities of the country. Third, the Estonian postcolonial predicament is explained. Fourth, postcolonial implications to the EU are brought to the forefront. The final section will conclude.

EU law (primacy) in Estonia – being a 'good European'

The starting point in the search for Estonian European constitutional imaginaries starts in its day-to-day positioning towards EU's autonomy and primacy claims. Estonia has been described in literature as one of the most open countries towards the EU's primacy claim inasmuch as it is brought as the closest example of European constitutional sovereignty, where a constitutional court of a Member State unconditionally accepts the standpoint of the CJEU on primacy.⁵ It has been described as employing an unconditionally EU-friendly approach⁶, being an example of exceptionless EU law primacy or even adhering to a doctrine of absolute primacy.⁷ This is due to very Eurofriendly Estonian Supreme Court (SC) practice.

The Eurofriendly understanding mainly stems from a SC opinion from 2006, where it ruled, at odds with most other EU highest courts, that if a provision of the Constitution is not compatible with EU law, its effects will be *suspended* without any explicit safeguards or emergency brakes.⁸ The Court stated that:

To find out which part of the Constitution is applicable, it has to be interpreted in conjunction with European Union law, which became binding for Estonia through the Accession Treaty. As such, only that part of the Constitution is applicable, which is in conformity with European Union law or which regulates the relationships that are not regulated by the European Union law. The effect of those provisions of the Constitution that are not compatible with the European Union law and thus inapplicable, is suspended. This means that within the spheres, which are within the exclusive competence of the European Union or where there is a shared competence with the European Union, European Union law shall apply in the case of a conflict between Estonian legislation, including the Constitution, with the European Union law.⁹

This interpretation has been called an 'unprecedented submissiveness to the EU' that has no counterparts to this 'bold expression of EU-fondness' in other EU Member States.¹⁰ Although there is an arguable shift of direction of the SC in recent years to a more cautious approach in the claim of EU law primacy over the Constitution¹¹, as there are in fact inbuilt constitutional guarantees that allow for

⁵ Damian Chalmers, Gareth Davies and Giorgio Monti, *European Union Law: Cases and Materials* (Second edition, Cambridge University Press 2010) 190–191. See discussion also in Tatjana Evas, 'Judicial reception of EU law in Estonia' in Bruno de Witte and others (eds), *National Courts and EU Law: New Issues, Theories and Methods* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2016) 154.

⁶ Madis Ernits and others, 'The Constitution of Estonia: The Unexpected Challenges of Unlimited Primacy of EU Law' in Anneli Albi and Samo Bardutzky (eds), *National Constitutions in European and Global Governance: Democracy, Rights, the Rule of Law* (TMC Asser Press 2019).

⁷ Anneli Albi and Hent Kalmo, 'Estonia: From Rules to Pragmatism' in Stefan Griller, Papadopoulou Lina and Puff Roman (eds), *National constitutions and EU integration* (2021) 4, 21.

⁸ Opinion of the Constitutional Review Chamber of the Supreme Court, 11.05.2006, 3-4-1-3-06, para 16; Order of the Constitutional Review Chamber of the Supreme Court, 26.06.2008, 3-4-1-5-08, para 30.

⁹ Opinion of the Constitutional Review Chamber of the Supreme Court, 11.05.2006, 3-4-1-3-06, para 16.

¹⁰ Julia Laffranque, 'A Glance at the Estonian Legal Landscape in View of the Constitution Amendment Act' (2007) XII *Juridica International* 55, 63.

¹¹ See for example the Judgement of the Supreme Court *en banc*, 15.12.2015, 3-2-1-71-14, paras 81-83, where the SC for the first time emphasised that compliance with EU law does not necessarily entail compliance with the Constitution and did not preclude constitutional review of a state aid decision priorly approved by the European

and condition Estonian EU membership. These are the fundamental principles that the Estonian Constitution is built on and that the membership of the EU is conditional to according to § 1 of the Constitution of the Republic of Estonia Amendment Act (CREAA), which was drafted and put on referendum for EU accession.¹² There are neverending intellectual debates on what these fundamental principles in fact are and there are different catalogs of different scholars, but the mostly agreed five principles include human dignity, democracy, the rule of law, the social state and the Estonian identity.¹³ But curiously the SC did not refer to them in its earlier case law on EU law primacy.

This controversy was recently clarified by the SC, that is the question on the inbuilt safeguard guarantees that condition Estonia's EU membership according to the CREAA § 1. The SC in a recent case clarified explicitly that 'the principle of primacy of EU law applies to the entirety of Estonian national law, including the Constitution, *but only insofar as this is not contrary to fundamental constitutional principles*.'¹⁴ This in fact clearly conditions EU law primacy to the fundamental constitutional principles of the Estonian Constitution. But there are still unresolved uncertainties whether these guarantees conditioned only the accession that took place at that moment in time or should be also used as an interpretative tool to possibly review EU acts' compliance with the fundamental principles of the Estonian Constitution at any point in time in the constitutional review process.¹⁵ These questions have not yet been answered by the SC.

The perception of Estonia as a 'good European' might either be confirmed or challenged also by other metrics. As such, Estonia can be characterised as a relatively inactive participant in the preliminary ruling system, with up to date only thirty nine preliminary questions referred to the CJEU and only four questions referred in 2022.¹⁶ Estonia is thus one of the countries with the lowest preliminary reference rate in the EU, following only Malta and Cyprus.¹⁷ This can indicate many things, but one possible explanation is that national courts (including the Supreme Court) do not want to enter into the preliminary ruling dialogue (or conflict) and specific questions are either sidelined or answered by the doctrine of consistent interpretation. Another metrics that can be considered is the number of infringement proceedings initiated against the state. Also in that data Estonia stands out as it has historically been a country with the least infringement proceedings.¹⁸

All this combined has created the narrative of an unreservedly Eurofriendly nation, which has its manifestations in a Europhile court practice, lukewarm preliminary reference enthusiasm and stellar infringement proceedings track-record. Thus, at least in the formal judicial field, reception and transposition of EU law has been generally favourable and the EU law primacy claim has been given almost absolute effect.

Commission. See also Judgement of the Administrative Law Chamber of the Supreme Court, 11.02.2009, 3-3-1-79-08, para 21.

¹² RT I 2003, 64, 429; RT I 2007, 43, 313.

¹³ See in Ernits and others (n 6) 889 discussion on different catalogs and debates.

¹⁴ Judgment of the Supreme Court *en banc*, 15.03.2022, 5-19-29, para 41, emphasis added.

¹⁵ See discussion: Ernits and others (n 6) 901; Tatjana Evas, 'Judicial Reception of EU Law in Estonia' in Bruno de Witte and others (eds), *National courts and EU law: new issues, theories and methods* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2016) 158.

¹⁶ See the statistics on the Supreme Court's website: <https://www.riigikohus.ee/et/cesti-kohtute-eelotsusetaotlused> (last accessed: 03.04.2023).

¹⁷ In 2018-2022 Estonia sent only a total of 14 preliminary references to the CJEU, lower numbers came only from Malta (1) and Cyprus (2). See statistics on the CJEU website: https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2023-03/stats_cour_2022_en.pdf (last accessed 03.04.2023).

¹⁸ See data in the CJEU webpage on actions for failure of a Member State to fulfil its obligations, where Estonia had zero actions in the period 2018-2022: https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2023-03/stats_cour_2022_en.pdf (last accessed 03.04.2023). See also data on openpolis report "InfringEye. Understanding EU infringement procedure through data", available at: https://www.openpolis.it/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/InfringEye_EdjiNet_openpolis.pdf (last accessed: 08.09.2022), p 7, 14, 22, 25, 34.

Securitization of sovereignty – ontological insecurity as the national impetus

The main paradigms to explain this unparalleled Eurofriendliness are security and sovereignty, something that might be conceptualized as the securitization of sovereignty – looking at sovereignty through the lens of security, prone to securitization. Here there emerges a noteworthy paradox that needs some explanation. On the one hand, Estonia has an exceptionally strong sovereignty clause in its constitution. This might be a legal representation of an inherent ‘ontological insecurity’ of statehood, sovereignty and security. On the other hand and as described above, it has had one of the most open and EU-friendly judicial interpretations of sovereignty in case-law. Estonia has been referred to as wanting to be seen as a ‘good European’, and has therefore implemented EU law without reservations and suspended the national constitution in areas that fall within the scope of EU law with courts having granted EU law exceptionless primacy.¹⁹

Sovereignty can be defined in many ways. Neil MacCormick has emphasised that the key idea of sovereignty is power without restriction.²⁰ The Estonian SC has defined it in the following sentence:

The core essence of sovereignty is the right of discretion in all matters, irrespective of external influences.²¹

The Constitution of the Republic of Estonia incorporates in its § 1(2) a particularly strong sovereignty clause: ‘The independence and sovereignty of Estonia are *timeless* and *inalienable*.’²² This has been called one of the strongest accentuations of in Europe²³ and perhaps even the world.²⁴ It has also been stressed that the fear of a rollback to a Soviet Union-type organisation was the main consideration behind the wording of § 1(2).²⁵

Despite this, the SC’s practice has been much more liberal and accommodating. The SC has treated sovereignty as a principle that is open to restrictions and weighing against other principles in the European Stability Mechanism (ESM) case:

Entry into international agreements is allowed by Chapter IX of the Constitution. If sovereignty is interpreted as absolute, entry into international agreements should not be allowed, because entering into international agreements always means restricting one's sovereignty to some extent. It follows that the Constitution does not require, despite the strict wording of the sovereignty clause, observation of absolute sovereignty. ... [M]embership of the EU and in international organisations has become a natural part of sovereignty in this day and age.²⁶

This has effectively been described in literature as a sign that despite such a ‘strong’ sovereignty clause in the Constitution, the SC has opted for a non-absolute interpretation of sovereignty meaning that it is open to restrictions and weighing of interests.²⁷ Such a restriction to sovereignty was in fact allowed as proportionate for the interests of the stability of the Eurozone by a narrow margin of only ten votes to nine in the ESM judgement.²⁸

¹⁹ Albi and Kalmo (n 7) 4.

²⁰ N. MacCormick, *Questioning sovereignty*, 1999, p 127.

²¹ SC 3-4-1-6-12, para 127.

²² The Constitution of the Republic of Estonia – RT 1992, 26, 349; RT I, 15.05.2015, 1, emphasis added.

²³ Anneli Albi, ‘Estonia’s Constitution and the EU: How and to What Extent to Amend It?’ (2002) VII *Juridica International* 39, 42.

²⁴ Ernits and others (n 6) 902.

²⁵ *Ibid*; Viljar Peep and Lemart Meri (eds), *Põhiseadus Ja Põhiseaduse Assamblee: Koguteos* (Juura 1997) 68.

²⁶ SC 3-4-1-6-12, para 130.

²⁷ See discussion in Ernits and others (n 6) 899.

²⁸ Judgement of the Supreme Court *en banc*, 12.07.2012, 3-4-1-6-12, paras 176–203 and 207–210.

It has been argued in literature that these profound narratives in Estonian constitutionalism are caused by the keenness to be ‘good Europeans’ due to acute geopolitical security concerns.²⁹ Albi and Kalmo have distinguished this as an poignant sense of anxiety about the fragility and precariousness of the independence, given Estonia’s geographical position on the border of Russia and the recent annexation of Crimea and the war in Ukraine.³⁰ The EU is thus regarded as the main (even if soft) security guarantee and there is a very real sense of responsibility amongst politicians and diplomats that any constitutional challenges to EU law, let alone any hint in the international media that Estonia might be un-cooperative or eurosceptic, could undermine potential support to the country in the future, should it be needed.³¹ As a consequence, Albi and Kalmo argue that Estonia and its legal community are not in a position to change the direction of travel because of geopolitical concerns and as in Estonia as well as the other Baltic states, membership in the EU is a part of a larger security strategy, and anything less than full compliance with its rules, albeit on solid constitutional grounds, are seen as playing with fire – in other words, a threat to sovereignty is taken to lie not in EU law but in a refusal to apply it (and the consequent diminished status of the country as a member).³² Maria Mälksoo has also claimed that the new Europeans are at the meeting point of modernity and postmodernity, where the urge to bolster state sovereignty clashes with the postmodernist security agendas of the organizations such as the EU and NATO, membership of which is at the same time considered to be the main basis for and the guarantee of their national security.³³

Sovereignty is obviously a complex concept, which additionally can have many different meanings across time and space. For example, it has been argued that sovereignty in Eastern Europe has had historically a different content than sovereignty in France or England.³⁴ When the former was established by a link between sovereignty and collective forms of human agency, the latter is argued to have been asserted in the absence of a social basis for it – sovereignty appears as a right that is granted and taken away depending upon the interests of outside powers.³⁵ This also has a postcolonial dimension as the doctrine of sovereign equality was historically in practice severally limited to colonial subjects. The contemporary notion of sovereignty has arguably undergone an even more fundamental transformation and cristallized as a post-Cold War revision of sovereignty as inherently conditional or limited. This is something that Maria Mälksoo has coined ‘vicarious sovereignty’ in her understanding of sovereignty as sovereignty achieved through sovereignty shared – a curious kind of sovereignty that emerges by the act of pooling national authority with other polities and thereby supposedly elevating state agency in international politics.³⁶ The view of sovereignty as non-absolute is widely supported and played out in Western Europe, but it has arguably created tensions in Eastern Europe. But perhaps not in Estonia?

1989 has been characterized as a return of sovereignty to Eastern Europe.³⁷ Was it also the departure of security? I claim not and security has always been the main imaginary binding people together and mobilising political action, at least in Estonia. And it has come back with the Russian neo-imperial ambitions and the war in Ukraine stronger than ever before.

This intertwinement of sovereignty and security concerns tilt the scales towards the preoccupations about security. Security can be defined in many ways and has even been argued to be an essentially contested

²⁹ Albi and Kalmo (n 7) 6.

³⁰ Ibid, 21.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Ibid, 37.

³³ Maria Mälksoo, *The Politics of Becoming European: A Study of Polish and Baltic Post-Cold War Security Imaginaries* (Routledge 2010) 68.

³⁴ Chris J Bickerton, ‘From Brezhnev to Brussels: Transformations of Sovereignty in Eastern Europe’ (2009) 46 *International Politics* 732, 734.

³⁵ *ibid.*

³⁶ Maria Mälksoo’s chapter in the edited volume, forthcoming, 7.

³⁷ Bickerton (n 34) 736.

concept.³⁸ Contemporary security studies define it broadly as a relative freedom from war, coupled with a relatively high expectation that defeat will not be a consequence of any war that should occur.³⁹ It has even been argued that in the face of uncertainty, states should assume the worst about other's intentions.⁴⁰ In today's context, where Russia is increasingly manifesting its neoimperial military ambitions, such assumptions are not merely theoretical any more and security has become the primary concern of many smaller Russia-bordering CEE countries. It has been argued that CEE countries naturally mistrust Russia and Russians because of given deep-seated identities and due to historical reasons, the Baltics *cannot but* 'securitize' their relations with Russia, which causes their relations with the West also to be understood in security terms.⁴¹

Identity is also prone to securitization as it is always possible to claim that as a result of a development, 'we will no longer be us', no longer the way we were or the way we ought to be to be true to our 'identity'.⁴² Securitization occurs if, by means of an argument about the priority and urgency of an existential threat, the issue is framed in terms of survival and therefore above politics.⁴³ This can also be argued in the realm of EU law and its primacy claims in Estonia. Estonian identity is evoked as an identity under an omnipresent threat of extinction and thus the geopolitical claims are embedded in identity narratives because arguments about location, cultural realms, and geopolitical threats are pivotal to the identity discourse.⁴⁴ The Estonian sovereignty discourse hinges on the question as to whether or not international integration strengthens Estonia's national security against the Russia threat.⁴⁵ The mainstream (and judicial) answer has been yes. Thus it has been argued that because of the Russian threat it is possible to represent European integration as a measure for strengthening state sovereignty.⁴⁶

Membership of both the EU and NATO is seen as the main guarantee of security against the Russia threat. Hereby also sovereignty is treated as a matter of security and identity⁴⁷ and thus open to concessions and negotiations. There is an identity-based nexus between sovereignty and security.⁴⁸ As sovereignty is framed in terms of existential threats to the Estonian nation and state⁴⁹, i.e. securitized, these concessions have been substantial. The institutionalization of sovereignty has found an idiosyncratic path. International integration is seen in Estonia not only as an option for the sovereign state but also as a *prerequisite* of state sovereignty; in other words the claim is not only that 'Estonia is a state and therefore it can integrate with Europe', but also that 'Estonia integrates with Europe and therefore Estonia is a state'.⁵⁰

Estonia is geographically the manifestation of a liminal borderland between the East and the West. Since 1989 it has made a huge ontological leap from being an eastern outpost in the West of the East to a

³⁸ David Carment, Stewart Prest and Yiagadeesen Samy, *Security, Development, and the Fragile State : Bridging the Gap between Theory and Policy* (Routledge 2010) 14.

³⁹ Bellamy, I. (1981) „Towards a Theory of International Security“, *Political Studies*, 29/1: 100-5, p 102.

⁴⁰ Alan Collins (ed), *Contemporary Security Studies* (Fifth edition, Oxford University Press 2019) 20.

⁴¹ Merje Kuus, 'Europe's Eastern Expansion and the Reinscription of Otherness in East-Central Europe' (2004) 28 *Progress in Human Geography* 472, 477; Raimo Väyrynen, 'The Security of the Baltic Countries: Cooperation and Defection' in Olaf F Knudsen (ed), *Stability and security in the Baltic Sea region: Russian, Nordic and European aspects* (Frank Cass 1999) 216.

⁴² Merje Kuus, 'European Integration in Identity Narratives in Estonia: A Quest for Security' (2002) 39 *Journal of Peace Research* 91, 93.

⁴³ *ibid.*

⁴⁴ *ibid* 95.

⁴⁵ Merje Kuus, 'Sovereignty for Security?: The Discourse of Sovereignty in Estonia' (2002) 21 *Political Geography* 393, 393.

⁴⁶ Kuus, 'European Integration in Identity Narratives in Estonia' (n 42) 103.

⁴⁷ *ibid* 100.

⁴⁸ Kuus, 'Sovereignty for Security?: The Discourse of Sovereignty in Estonia' (n 45) 398.

⁴⁹ *ibid* 395.

⁵⁰ *ibid* 398.

western outpost in the East of the West.⁵¹ Such borderlandness together with the small size of the country has created ontological anxieties – anxieties over being – about statehood and the very existing. It has been claimed that sovereignty in Estonia is conceptually linked to not just the state, but, rather, nation and ethnicity.⁵² The Hungarian political scientist István Bibó has called this an *existential anxiety for the community* in his essay ‘Miseries of East European Small States’:

This is the situation that gave rise to a characteristic feature of the unbalanced Central-Eastern European political mentality: *existential anxiety for the community*. East European nations were always overshadowed by alien, rootless state powers either bearing European forms or wielding unbearable pressure, whether they were called emperor, tsar, or sultan, [---] They all got to know the feeling when alien powers endangered, seized, or ruled their sacred places of national history and suppressed or governed their people in whole or in part. They all had territories for which they were justified in being anxious or in claiming, and all have been close to partial or full destruction. ‘The death of the nation’ or ‘the annihilation of the nation’ rings empty in West European ears; Westerners can imagine extermination, subjection, or slowly going native, but political ‘annihilation’ overnight is sheer bombast to them, yet it is a *palpable reality* for the nations of Eastern Europe. Here there is no need to exterminate or expel a nation to make it feel endangered; it is enough to call *its existence into doubt* with a sufficiently aggressive rhetoric.⁵³

Unlike the Western European big powers, the little Eastern European nations have historically lived in fear of their own extinction.⁵⁴ Contemporary IR theory conceptualizes this sense of feeling threatened as *ontological insecurity*. Ontological insecurity is the flipside of ontological security conceptualised as a sense of confidence or trust about the basic existential parameters of self and social identity.⁵⁵ The mirror notion of ontological insecurity is thus a state of uncertainty about one’s identity and place in the world, leading to an upset sense of agency.⁵⁶ Ontological insecurity is triggered by normative threats – threats that go beyond physical, material damage and promises to destruct something essential about one’s group or nation⁵⁷ – that explicitly disturb an actor’s ‘security as being’.⁵⁸ Thus the notion of sovereignty and its interaction with security function both as a reason for European integration and as a result of integration.⁵⁹ But it also means that on the flipside, the argument that EU membership necessarily strengthens state sovereignty would collapse if the Russia threat were removed.⁶⁰ At least for now, this is not a possibility that might come into existence.

The Estonian postcolonial setting – coloniality in the past and in the present

With the dissolution of the major empires after the First World War, Eastern Europe became the site of the first major decolonization of the twentieth century.⁶¹ This short period of decolonization was soon

⁵¹ Heiko Pääbo, ‘Estonian Transformation. From an Eastern Outpost in the West to a Western Outpost in the East’ in Barbara Törnquist-Plewa and Krzysztof Stala (eds), *Cultural Transformations after Communism: Central and Eastern Europe in Focus* (Nordic Academic Press, Sweden 2011).

⁵² Kuus, ‘Sovereignty for Security?: The Discourse of Sovereignty in Estonia’ (n 45) 395.

⁵³ István Bibó, *The Art of Peacemaking: Political Essays by Istvan Bibo* (Péter Pásztor tr, Yale University Press 2015) 149–150.

⁵⁴ Mälksoo (n 33) 43; Tony Judt, ‘The Past Is Another Country: Myth and Memory in Postwar Europe’ (1992) 121 *Daedalus* 83, 105.

⁵⁵ Giddens Anthony, *The Constitution of Society: Outline of the Theory of Structuration* (Polity Press 1984) 375; Maria Mälksoo, ‘The Normative Threat of Subtle Subversion: The Return of “Eastern Europe” as an Ontological Insecurity Trope’ (2019) 32 *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 365, 366.

⁵⁶ Mälksoo (n 55) 366.

⁵⁷ Ingrid Creppell, ‘The Concept of Normative Threat’ (2011) 3 *International Theory* 450, 452.

⁵⁸ Mälksoo (n 55) 368–369.

⁵⁹ Kuus, ‘Sovereignty for Security?: The Discourse of Sovereignty in Estonia’ (n 45) 403.

⁶⁰ *ibid* 407.

⁶¹ James Mark and Paul Betts, ‘Introduction’ in James Mark and Paul Betts (eds), *Socialism Goes Global: The Soviet Union and Eastern Europe in the Age of Decolonisation* (OUP 2022) 2.

followed after the Second World War by another imperial project (although claiming anti-imperialism as its character) – the Soviet Union. But the Soviet Union too fell. That means that Eastern Europe is a region of nations that have twice liberated themselves from empires.⁶² In this general background Estonia is a particular example of anti-colonial struggles as it has throughout its history always an imperial subject of numerous colonial entities, never itself exemplifying any imperial ambitions or capabilities. This factor sets it apart even from some other CEE countries, which have led imperial constellations (e.g. Hungary in the Hapsburg Empire) or fantasized about gaining overseas possessions themselves (Czechoslovakia and Poland)⁶³ that might trigger nostalgies of grandness and neo-imperial line of thought.

Arguably, the demise of the Soviet empire is still ongoing as the war in Ukraine has manifested – Russia has still to reckon with its own colonial past and overcome instances of neo-imperialism. Thus, the talk of empires is still very much affecting the everyday functionings of states, nations and transnational entities of which Estonia and the EU are just one example.

In order to understand the above described changes in Estonian European constitutional imaginaries, its postcolonial setting should be acknowledged. This relates to not only Soviet colonialism, but also the preceding Baltic German and Czarist Russian colonialisms.⁶⁴ This has been called an experience of triple colonization.⁶⁵ Of course, this is not the only predicament characterising its history and presence. Nor is it a call to add to the many existing victimhood claims. It is just a fascinating case study of a truly postcolonial predicament. In fact it has been emphasised that a great many processes are taking place simultaneously in Estonia: de-colonization, de-sovietization, re-nationalization, re-Europeanization, globalization and postmodernization.⁶⁶ And although EU's own legacies of empire and imperialism are starting to slowly feature in literature⁶⁷, there is still little to no accounts on what postcoloniality means and entails for singular EU Member States and their place in contemporary Europe. It is not often that Estonia or other post-Soviet countries are thought of in postcolonial terms. That is because of some practical and conceptual difficulties in applying the framework to the post-Soviet sphere.

Colonialism may be defined as referring to a political, economic and cultural control over a territory by a foreign power.⁶⁸ In a similar vein, the pioneering Edward Said has explained imperialism: 'At some very basic level, imperialism means thinking about, setting on, controlling land that you do not possess, that is distant, that is lived on and owned by others.'⁶⁹ One main counterargument to applying postcolonial thought to the Baltics is that from the orientalist lens, Russia is not Western enough and the European parts of its colonies were not non-Western at all.⁷⁰ If in Central Asia the Soviet colonisers were considered

⁶² *ibid.*

⁶³ *ibid.* 12.

⁶⁴ See on the different decolonial struggles further: Epp Annus, 'From the Birth of Nations to the European Union: Colonial and Decolonial Developments in the Baltic Region' in Dittmar Schorkowitz, John R Chávez and Ingo W Schröder (eds), *Shifting Forms of Continental Colonialism* (Springer Singapore 2019).

⁶⁵ Piret Peiker, 'Estonian Nationalism through the Postcolonial Lens' in Epp Annus (ed), *Coloniality, nationality, modernity: a postcolonial view on Baltic cultures under Soviet rule* (Routledge 2018) 114. Throughout history there have actually been also other colonizers – such as Swedes, Danes and Polish-Lithuanians – and the Baltic zone had witnessed complex entanglements of different colonial rulers, which in national narratives formed hierarchies of better and worse times – i.e. the Swedish rule was remembered as "good", while the Soviet rule a "bad" time. See: Epp Annus, 'Layers of Colonial Rule in the Baltics: Nation-Building, the Soviet Rule and the Affectivity of a Nation' in Dirk Göttische and Axel Dunker (eds), *(Post-) Colonialism across Europe: Transcultural History and National Memory* (Aisthesis Verlag 2020) 366–367.

⁶⁶ Maire Jaanus, 'Estonia's Time and Monumental Time' in Violeta Kelertas (ed), *Baltic Postcolonialism* (BRILL 2006) 203.

⁶⁷ Signe Rehling Larsen, 'European Public Law after Empires' (2022) 1 *European Law Open* 6.

⁶⁸ Epp Annus, 'Between Arts and Politics: A Postcolonial View on Baltic Cultures of the Soviet Era' in Epp Annus (ed), *Coloniality, nationality, modernity: a postcolonial view on Baltic cultures under Soviet rule* (Routledge 2018) 2.

⁶⁹ Edward W Said, *Culture and Imperialism* (Chatto and Windus 1993) 7.

⁷⁰ Epp Annus, 'The Problem of Soviet Colonialism in the Baltics' (2012) 43 *Journal of Baltic Studies* 21, 24.

Europeans, in the Baltics they were understood to be opposed to European civilization.⁷¹ In particular the Baltics have historically identified rather with European than a Third World sphere of interest.⁷² But this does not necessarily exclude the European parts of Soviet imperium from a colonial setting. Although postcolonial theory was initially a critique of Western power, the West has hardly monopolized colonial activity.⁷³ This has been described as a paradox at the center of much of mainstream postcolonial theory: the Western hegemonic assumptions on ‘the Rest’, it has mostly maintained a Western-centrism.⁷⁴ It is worth to think of decolonizing postcolonial studies in that sense. As such also Imperial Russia and the Soviet Union were empires in their day, with their own subalterns, their own claims to civilizational superiority, their own political economies of inequality, and their contemporary legacies for both the conquerors and the conquered.⁷⁵ But of course, there was still something inherently *different* in those empires. David Chioni Moore has argued that the Baltic and Central European states are a distinct form of colonialism what he calls ‘reverse-cultural colonization’⁷⁶ whereby the relationship between colonizers and colonized is marked by an ironic reversal.⁷⁷ He argues that in Russian-Central European colonization orientalizing is reversed because for several centuries Russia has been saddled with the fear or belief that it was culturally inferior to the West.⁷⁸ And in return, the Central European often saw the colonizing Russo-Soviets as Asiatics⁷⁹ and felt themselves superior to Russians and the Baltic Republics represented even an ‘outpost of Western civilization’.⁸⁰

Thus there is some inherent secondarity in the core of the Russo-Soviet imperialism. The secondary empire of Russia/Soviet Union has also been called a Janus-faced empire in that it has always been mimicking and dependent on Western modernity doomed to try to catch up with Europe and prove that it can out-West the West.⁸¹ The Janus-facedness rolls out in Russia as a paradigmatic case of a second-class empire: rich yet poor, providential yet failed, an empire with a long and unsuccessful history of external appropriation of certain elements of modernity on a different basis – non-capitalist, non-western, not based on Western Christianity or a Latin-derived language.⁸² This has been conceptualised also as an ‘empire in between’.⁸³ And it has implications for its colonies. It has been argued that this subaltern empire, feeling itself a colony in the presence of the West, then compensates its inferiority complex onto its colonies.⁸⁴ Račevskis has stressed that if the Soviet form of colonialism differed from other kinds it was perhaps in the brutality and thoroughness of its oppression which he further qualifies as totalitarian colonialism.⁸⁵ But the situation remains nevertheless a colonial one.

Another point of contestation lies in the question whether it is possible to colonize a modern industrialized nation state, which the Baltics were by 1940s. Is it a fundamental condition for the acceptability of a

⁷¹ Annus, ‘Layers of Colonial Rule in the Baltics: Nation-Building, the Soviet Rule and the Affectivity of a Nation’ (n 69) 362.

⁷² Karlis Racevskis, ‘Toward a Postcolonial Perspective on the Baltic States’ in Violeta Kelertas (ed), *Baltic Postcolonialism* (BRILL 2006) 166.

⁷³ David Chioni Moore, ‘Is the Post- in Postcolonial the Post- in Post-Soviet? Toward a Global Postcolonial Critique’ (2001) 116 *Modern Language Association* 111, 114.

⁷⁴ Kevork Oskanian, ‘Conceptualising an Empire in Between’ in Kevork Oskanian (ed), *Russian Exceptionalism between East and West* (Springer International Publishing 2021) 21.

⁷⁵ *ibid.* 22.

⁷⁶ Moore (n 77) 121.

⁷⁷ Racevskis (n 76) 166.

⁷⁸ Moore (n 77) 121.

⁷⁹ *ibid.*

⁸⁰ Annus, ‘The Problem of Soviet Colonialism in the Baltics’ (n 74) 26. See also: Heiko Pääbo, ‘From an Eastern Outpost in the West to a Western Outpost in the East’ 27.

⁸¹ Madina Tlostanova, ‘Postsocialist ≠ Postcolonial? On Post-Soviet Imaginary and Global Coloniality’ (2012) 48 *Journal of Postcolonial Writing* 130, 135.

⁸² *ibid.*

⁸³ Oskanian (n 78).

⁸⁴ Tlostanova (n 85) 135.

⁸⁵ Racevskis (n 76) 168, 174.

colonial situation that the colonized people are ‘uncivilized’?⁸⁶ Russian colonial rule arguably lacked a philosophical stance to justify its conquests as civilizing missions, instead an opposing narrative emerged: the Baltics as the developed West of the Soviet Union.⁸⁷ Annus distills it down to an identity question and argues that the Sovietization of Estonia included a distortion of national memory and strict control over cultural production.⁸⁸

A related third question related to the previous one is whether the annexation of the Baltics in the summer of 1940 should be properly called occupation or colonization. Colonization is the process of the process of taking lands and resources for exploitation whereas according to the 1907 Hague convention article 42 a territory is considered occupied when it is actually placed under the authority of the hostile army.⁸⁹ What helps in determining this is the differentiation of the concepts of ‘colonization’ and ‘colonialism’, the former being a process of territorial acquisition and the latter a system of domination.⁹⁰ Annus thus characterizes that what happened in the Baltics was a military occupation of a modern industrial nation state followed by the exploitation of local resources and the arrival of new settlers – a colonial situation.⁹¹ She proposes that even though the Soviet Union occupied, rather than colonized the Baltic States, the period of occupation nevertheless developed into a period of colonial rule with foreign supremacy and military control; reconstruction of the economy of the territory in order to serve the interests of the colonizers; appropriation of goods and products from the colonized territories to the centre of the empire, and careful screening of cultural activities.⁹²

All in all, scholars have come to the conclusion that it is meaningful to talk about Soviet postcolonialism and see the Soviet Union as a colonial enterprise.⁹³ When colonialism is taken to involve a condition of domination, of territorial occupation and control⁹⁴, then there is no grounds to deny Soviet colonialism. David Chioni Moore has even emphasised ‘first, how extraordinarily postcolonial the societies of the former Soviet regions are, and, second, how extraordinarily little attention is paid to this fact’.⁹⁵

But if there are such hurdles in applying postcolonial theory to the Baltic post-Soviet experience, why would it matter at all? What is the added benefit of a postcolonial lens in the specific case of Estonia in the EU? That can be answered with many different arguments.

One aspect of postcoloniality is also the construction of identity and the hierarchies it creates. In Estonia this played out as the feeling of superiority over the colonizing Russian nation. This can be seen as a reversal of the usual colonizer-colonized roles. The Estonians always regarded themselves as the Westerners of the Soviet Union.⁹⁶ In identerian terms, for the Estonians the Russians were the primary ‘other’, embodying a set of characteristics that were the opposite of what constitutes Estonianness.⁹⁷ Postcolonial methodological framework also helps to formulate certain key themes and concepts such as structures of exclusion/inclusion (the centre/periphery model and theorizations of the liminal and ‘in-between’); formations of nationalism, structures of othering and representations of difference; forms and

⁸⁶ Annus, ‘The Problem of Soviet Colonialism in the Baltics’ (n 74) 33.

⁸⁷ *ibid* 34.

⁸⁸ *ibid* 35.

⁸⁹ *ibid* 28.

⁹⁰ Jürgen Osterhammel, *Colonialism: A Theoretical Overview* (Markus Wiener Publishers 2005) 4; Jaak Kangilaski, ‘Postcolonial Theory as a Means to Understand Estonian Art History’ in Epp Annus (ed), *Coloniality, nationality, modernity: a postcolonial view on Baltic cultures under Soviet rule* (Routledge 2018) 34.

⁹¹ Annus, ‘The Problem of Soviet Colonialism in the Baltics’ (n 74) 31, 35.

⁹² *ibid* 36–37.

⁹³ Annus, ‘The Problem of Soviet Colonialism in the Baltics’ (n 74); Epp Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (Routledge 2018); Racevskis (n 76).

⁹⁴ Racevskis (n 76) 167.

⁹⁵ Moore (n 77) 114.

⁹⁶ Sigrid Rausing, *History, Memory, and Identity in Post-Soviet Estonia: The End of a Collective Farm* (Oxford University Press 2004) 2.

⁹⁷ *Ibid*, 5.

historical realizations of anti-colonial struggle; the experience of trauma; resistance as a complex of cultural practices; alterity; ambivalence; self-colonization; cultural geography; dislocation; minority and subaltern cultures; neocolonialism; orientalizing; transnationalism, etc.⁹⁸ Many of these speak to the Estonian case in particular. Most notably, the anti-colonial struggle materializes in a deservably hawkish approach to Russia and the Russian aggression in Ukraine in particular. This has caused frictions and tensions in its relationship with the Western European nations, who often advocate for a more balanced or nuanced approach.

The postcolonial lens may answer many questions and explain also the sovereignty-security tensions in the Estonian context. If the essence of postcolonialism is the struggle for freedom and emancipation, restitution and reconciliation from current or former imperial powers then the Estonian postcolonial predicament is evident. The strive for an independent, intact and *secure* country permeates every aspect and action of society and politics. The anguishes of the former colonial rule are embedded in the national psyche and consciousness so deeply, that even a slightest threat of the return of the Russian rule and empire cut to the core of the national self-awareness. The antidote of Russia and Rusianness is Europe and Europeanness. Being a ‘good European’ thus directly emanates from the postcolonial condition of alienating from and juxtaposing to the former imperial power. The transformation is all-encompassing. Estonia has migrated from the West of the East to the East of the West.⁹⁹ And in identarian terms, Russia has become the main European ‘other’.¹⁰⁰

Issues of nationalism and statehood also play to the heart of postcoloniality. In the Soviet-era Baltic states the loss of national self-determination and the colonial overwriting of national histories defined the Baltic experience of the Soviet regime and also in decolonization processes, national remobilization was a crucial factor.¹⁰¹ Thus, while CEE is often described as more nationalist in their outlook, this nationalism should be put to context, in the context of the histories of decolonization. The postcolonial aspects of nationalism do not necessarily pathologize it as tribal or box it as a ‘moral mistake’, but instead see its role as an anti-imperial force.¹⁰² It also puts into context the arguable clash between Western vs Eastern values with regard to nationalism (or what in the East is often rather called patriotism) in that it takes into account the former’s colonial baggage and latter’s decolonial struggles. In particular, the Estonian experience of triple colonization shape the present-day Estonian definitions of collective self and influence present political and sociocultural imagination.¹⁰³ This links back to issues of sovereignty and security as the concern about sovereignty does not always disappear with decolonization, as (perceived or realistic) foreign threat and/or indirect forms of domination still remain – this breeds vibrant nationalism.¹⁰⁴ Thus there is a valid distinction between nationalisms and nationhoods that have called themselves into being through a struggle against a clear and present colonial power and those that have not.¹⁰⁵ Nationalism for postcolonial states is about the preservice of the state and not about the expansion of the state.

Postcoloniality could also be thought of in contemporary terms and conditions and with regard to the EU. As coloniality can be described by matrixes of power and domination, the EU also has a certain power over its Member States. This lies in the answer of the question, can the EU be thought of as an empire and is Estonia subject to another peripheralization? Jose Manuel Barroso has characterized the EU as the ‘first non-imperial empire’¹⁰⁶, the imperial nature of the European project has also fascinated and

⁹⁸ Dorota Kołodziejczyk and Cristina Şandru, ‘Introduction: On Colonialism, Communism and East-Central Europe – Some Reflections’ (2012) 48 *Journal of Postcolonial Writing* 113, 113.

⁹⁹ Epp Annus, chapter in edited volume, forthcoming.

¹⁰⁰ Iver B Neumann, ‘Russia as Europe’s Other’ (1998) 6 *Journal of Area Studies* 26.

¹⁰¹ Annus, ‘Between Arts and Politics: A Postcolonial View on Baltic Cultures of the Soviet Era’ (n 72) 5.

¹⁰² Peiker (n 69) 114.

¹⁰³ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁴ *ibid* 119.

¹⁰⁵ *ibid* 126.

¹⁰⁶ Honor Mahony, ‘Barroso Says EU Is an “Empire”’ *EUobserver* (Brussels, 7 November 2007) <<https://euobserver.com/eu-political/24458>> accessed 8 September 2022.

convinced other scholars.¹⁰⁷ And although it is readily acknowledged that Soviet influence was a kind of colonialism, there is much less willingness to examine Western policies toward CEE in terms of postcoloniality.¹⁰⁸ But this condition has nevertheless prompted description of the region as ‘doubly postcolonial’: the object of both (former) Soviet imperialism (and the current threat of Russian neo-imperialism) and Western ‘peripheralizing capitalism’.¹⁰⁹ This plays out as on the one hand addressing the former colonizers/occupants venturing a postcolonial project of reclamation (of own history and voice) targeting the former imperial power; at the same time, however, addressing the West in a most ambivalent postcolonial mode, in which the West is both historically complicit with the political subjugation of the region behind the Iron Curtain and at the same time functioning at present as a peripheralizing metropolis.¹¹⁰ Merje Kuus has called the 2004 Eastern European EU enlargement as underpinned by broadly orientalist discourse and stressed that the fact that Eastern Europe was not formally colonized by West European powers does not preclude the relevance of postcolonial theory to CEE.¹¹¹ EU law generally has been argued to have further peripheralizing effects on the already peripheries.¹¹² This status has also been described as an in-betweenness of the colonial and anti-colonial worlds: associating with the (Western) core and often seeking to ape its values and achievements, whilst also fearing colonization and identifying with others who resisted it and seeking to provide its own more vital alternative.¹¹³ But still it must be stressed that the EU’s regime has not been forced on Member States from the outside as the membership is completely voluntary and exit is possible.¹¹⁴

This marks the postcolonial sensibility in the way CEE articulates itself vis-à-vis the European Union: how it claims to be inherently European and at the same time manifests its separateness.¹¹⁵

Layers of colonialism – Postcolonial implications to the European project

Coloniality in today’s Europe can be thought of as layered – Europe as the sum of its parts with different experiences and relationships with colonialism and the EU itself as a possibly at least partly with neo-colonial characteristics. This mix of postcoloniality and neo-coloniality has implications for the European project and for the EU specifically. But where does it leave the EU as a constellation in the vocabulary of coloniality?

The EU itself too has to reckon with its identity. The creation of identity implies the establishment of a difference, difference which is often constructed on the basis of a hierarchy, i.e. every identity is relational and the affirmation of a difference is a precondition for the existence of any identity, the perception of something ‘other’ which constitutes its exterior.¹¹⁶ This ‘other’ can be thought of on geographic as well as conceptual terms. Geographically Europe’s other has been the ‘orient’ in its entirety as opposed to the West or the ‘occident’. In this sense Europe can be defined negatively: Europe is what Asia is not.¹¹⁷ In

¹⁰⁷ Jan Zielonka, *Europe as Empire: The Nature of the Enlarged European Union* (Oxford University Press 2006); Jan Zielonka, ‘Europe as a Global Actor: Empire by Example?’ (2008) 84 *International Affairs* (Royal Institute of International Affairs 1944-) 471; Kalypso Nicolaïdis, Benny Sèbe and Gabrielle Maas (eds), *Echoes of Empire: Memory, Identity and Colonial Legacies* (IB Tauris 2015); Hartmut Behr and Yannis Stivachtis (eds), *Revisiting the European Union as Empire* (1st edn, Routledge 2015).

¹⁰⁸ Kuus, ‘Europe’s Eastern Expansion and the Reinscription of Otherness in East-Central Europe’ (n 41) 475.

¹⁰⁹ Mark and Betts (n 65) 10; Kołodziejczyk and Şandru (n 102) 115.

¹¹⁰ Kołodziejczyk and Şandru (n 102) 115.

¹¹¹ Kuus, ‘Europe’s Eastern Expansion and the Reinscription of Otherness in East-Central Europe’ (n 41) 482–483.

¹¹² Damjan Kukovec, ‘Law and the Periphery’ (2015) 21 *European Law Journal* 406.

¹¹³ Mark and Betts (n 65) 11.

¹¹⁴ As a remark it should be brought out that purely formally, exit from the Soviet Union was also possible on paper (i.e. by law), but it was still de facto impossible. One could compare this to the painful experiences of Brexit and the UK’s withdrawal from the EU and the strategies adopted therein.

¹¹⁵ Kołodziejczyk and Şandru (n 102) 115.

¹¹⁶ Chantal Mouffe, *On the Political* (Routledge 2005) 15.

¹¹⁷ F. Fitzpatrick and J. H. Bergeron, *Europe’s Other: European Law Between Modernity and Postmodernity*. 1998, p 31, Helderling, 1987, 93.

this 'logic' of identity, Asia provides both the point of constant difference to Europe yet is also able to become the same as Europe.¹¹⁸ Russia has been specifically the constitutive other for Europe.¹¹⁹ The geographical boundaries of this East-West distinction are however blurred and have undergone a significant transformation since the end of the Cold War – i.e. Europe's bounds have remained chronically uncertain, especially in their eastern definition.¹²⁰

Here orientalism enters also in the conceptual relationship between Western and Eastern Europe. Orientalism as novelled in Edward Said's landmark study, is essentially a particular Western style of defining, dominating, restructuring and having authority over the Orient that produces the alleged Western superiority and hegemony over the East.¹²¹ This applies also to the in-between Eastern Europe. Eastern Europe has been treated by the West as 'European but not quite European' and approached with a 'Western chauvinism'.¹²² The notion of Eastern Europe has been the embodiment of liminality, the state of in-betweenness in Europe's self-image and identity creation.¹²³ Indeed, Western Europe 'invented' Eastern Europe as its complementary other half in the eighteenth century, locating it on the developmental scale that measured the distance between civilization and barbarism.¹²⁴ Thus the coloniality aspect becomes further layered as first, Soviet colonialism is the Baltic historical predicament, and second, Western colonialism demonstrates its colors in the post-Cold War relations between the East and the West.

The liminal in-between Estonia makes a firm transition from the 'West of the East' to the 'East of the West'¹²⁵, still by definition preserving its inherent Eastness also when belonging to the West. And that brings in colonial undertones in the relations between East and West¹²⁶, traced for example in the security domain by Maria Mälksoo with regard to Poland and the Baltics.¹²⁷

The East can be here characterized also as 'better Europe', free from guilt for the sins of the continent's colonialism.¹²⁸ Having been only a colonial subject, it brings along idiosyncratic experiences and sensibilities, which can be instructive for Western Europe with a different past with coloniality. But this might need some further qualification as also some countries in the East have an imperial legacy (e.g. Hungary, Poland, even (a part of) Latvia has had a colony for a short period of time in history¹²⁹). Estonia is different in that it really never throughout history has had any imperial or colonial ambitions. Thus its experience as a 'good European' with a history of pure colonial subjectivism might be a source of inspiration and novel rethinking of the European project too.

But besides the geographical, there is also a conceptual other written into the European project. The conceptual 'other' of the EU is often referred to as nationalism or the 'nation'. The 'nation' is something that the EU claims to transcend and that is not only the particularity against which a generalized European identity is created, but also the fragmented contrary against which a unified EU law is constituted.¹³⁰ Europe's basic premise is that nationalism brought the continent to the point of ruin in the twentieth

¹¹⁸ Ibid, 32.

¹¹⁹ Neumann (n 104).

¹²⁰ Fitzpatrick and Bergeron (n 117) 33.

¹²¹ Edward W Said, *Orientalism* (Penguin Books 2003) 3; Mälksoo (n 33) 56.

¹²² Mälksoo (n 33) 56, 59.

¹²³ ibid 57.

¹²⁴ Larry Wolff, *Inventing Eastern Europe: The Map of Civilization on the Mind of the Enlightenment* (Stanford University Press 1994); Mälksoo (n 33) 57.

¹²⁵ Epp Annus chapter in the edited volume, forthcoming.

¹²⁶ Georgeta Pourchot, 'EU's Eastern "Empire"' in Hartmut Behr and Yannis Stivachtis (eds), *Revisiting the European Union as empire* (1st edn, Routledge 2015) 18.

¹²⁷ Mälksoo (n 33).

¹²⁸ Mark and Betts (n 65) 9.

¹²⁹ Racevskis (n 76) 182.

¹³⁰ Fitzpatrick and Bergeron (n 117), xii.

century.¹³¹ As such, nationalism is relegated to the realm of the primitive¹³² - there is a constellation of malign attributes associated with the nation-state and national sovereignty such as war, decay, nationalism, politics, and these are arranged against a benign EU intrinsically associated with contrar attributes such as integration, peace, cosmopolitanism, progress and law.¹³³

Estonia and possibly other postcolonial CEE countries on the opposite, celebrate the nation as they have historically had limited and externally constrained relationship with it. Nationalism takes the form of patriotism in many parts of CEE and the nation is carefully protected and celebrated in this part of the continent. Piret Peiker has distinguished between nationalisms and nationhoods that have called themselves into being through a struggle against a clear and present colonial power and those that have not.¹³⁴ These nationalisms are different. The colonial past necessarily forms a part of the national present.¹³⁵

However, in all this and paradoxically, the EU is argued to take and vigorously promote the attributes of the nation.¹³⁶ This provides for a distinct European identity in that it joins two momentous effects: the progressive elimination of internal or national boundaries within the EU and the increasingly draconian enunciation of an 'external' boundary around the EU, setting it against certain excluded 'others'.¹³⁷ In that the EU takes on an identity that seems indistinguishable from that of nation: it both contains and is contained by nation, and furthermore it is 'like' nation.¹³⁸ Thus, both the EU and its Member States conform to the characters of nation and the Court of Justice is engaging successfully in a modernist mission of state formation.¹³⁹ This is a paradox at the heart of the European project - how can an entity at the same time fight against and try to become something.

In order for Europe to become whole, both the geographical and conceptual othering of a large part of its official self should see its heyday. Eastern Europe in its inherent being or its steadfast convictions cannot be the European Other no longer nor can the nation as the ultimate conceptual Other. Understandings of sovereignty, security and EU law primacy claims play an important part in this. As shown in the paper, the sovereignty understandings might not in fact diverge as much as often thought. But security imaginaries yes. If war is a distant memory for Western Europe, it is a constant very real contingency in the East. Neoimperial Russia is both best understood and most fiercely dreaded in Eastern Europe. The West is dragging along. This has all played out all too vividly in Ukraine.

Conclusions

This paper has argued that the securitization of sovereignty as played out by the Estonian need and want to be a 'good European' has been caused at least partly by its postcolonial predicament. This has further caused different understandings of nation and nationalism and a more hawkish approach to Russian neo-imperialism. All this plays a role in the European self-understanding too. Europe should reckon with the experiences of its Eastern flank and listen more carefully to CEE's concerns regarding Russia, but also of the sensitive topic of nationalism (or as the East calls it: patriotism).

For Europe to be whole, it needs to acknowledge and respond to the sensitivities of all its constitutive parts. And postcoloniality plays a big role in this. As most countries in CEE have a stronger or weaker

¹³¹ Vincent Della Sala, 'Europe's Odyssey?: Political Myth and the European Union' (2016) 22 *Nations & Nationalism* 524, 532.

¹³² Fitzpatrick and Bergeron (n 117), 24.

¹³³ *Ibid*, 36.

¹³⁴ Piret Peiker, 'Estonian Nationalism through the Postcolonial Lens' in Epp Annus (ed), *Coloniality, nationality, modernity: a postcolonial view on Baltic cultures under Soviet rule* (Routledge 2018) 126.

¹³⁵ *ibid* 127.

¹³⁶ Fitzpatrick and Bergeron (n 117), 27.

¹³⁷ *Ibid*, 34.

¹³⁸ *Ibid*, 36, 38.

¹³⁹ *Ibid*, 39.

post-Soviet sensibility in their national psyche. Estonia being one of them with one of the most acute sense of security self-awareness that translates into a distinctive understanding of sovereignty and European integration. It is important to stress that the memberships in NATO and the EU were for many Estonian pursued not (only) as aims in themselves, but as an escape route from the economic and political sphere of influence of Russia, continuously perceived to have colonial ambitions.¹⁴⁰ These ambitions have painfully materialised in recent years and this has given many CEE countries the moral standpoint to say ‘told you so’ and the West having to acknowledge shortcomings in their approach to Russia.¹⁴¹

Thus, there is an evident postcolonial sensibility in the way CEE broadly and Estonia more precisely articulates both its recent past and its embattled present: how it places itself at the heart of the European project yet at the same time feels acutely, and seeks to articulate and manifest, its separateness; how it struggles to rememorize, rewrite and reinterpret its history, both more distant and more recent; and how it negotiates its continued semi-peripheral status in the EU.¹⁴² The way in which the EU positions itself vis-a-vis such CEE countries matters. As one Estonian official has put it: ‘The EU is just another empire. We are going from one empire to another.’¹⁴³ This should be remembered by the EU and its Western European actors. And maybe Europe does need a new utopia.¹⁴⁴ A new constitutive ‘other’ beyond nationalism and Eastern Europe to become a cohesive ‘Self’.

¹⁴⁰ Peiker (n 69) 121.

¹⁴¹ ‘European Commission president: We should have listened to Baltics about Russia’ *ERR*, 14 September 2022, <<https://news.err.ee/1608715891/eu-commission-president-we-should-have-listened-to-baltics-about-russia>> accessed 12 April 2023.

¹⁴² Cristina Şandru, ‘Postcolonial Postcommunism?’ in Anna Bernard, Ziad Elmarsafy and Stuart Murray (eds), *What Postcolonial Theory Doesn’t Say* (Routledge 2015) 169.

¹⁴³ As quoted in Gregory Feldman, ‘Culture, State, and Security in Europe: The Case of Citizenship and Integration Policy in Estonia’ (2005) 32 *American Ethnologist* 676, 679. Also Estonian far-right politicians have compared the EU with the Soviet Union: ‘Mart Helme: Nothing scandalous about comparing EU to the Soviet Union’ *ERR*, 24 July 2019, <<https://news.err.ee/964232/martin-helme-nothing-scandalous-about-comparing-eu-to-soviet-union>> accessed 12 April 2023.

¹⁴⁴ Marju Lauristin, ‘The European Public Sphere and the Social Imaginary of the “New Europe”’ (2007) 22 *European Journal of Communication* 397, 407.